

Modeling of Brain Metabolism Energy for Diagnosis Cortical Spreading Depression by Matlab Simulink

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Abstract— Modeling brain Ischemia is an essential tool to understand brain energy metabolism and brain chemical reaction during ischemia. In this study, we are to construct and test a mathematical model capable of simulating changes in brain energy metabolism and develop Simulink application for modeling ischemia in different pathophysiological conditions. The model consists of metabolic parameters such as cerebral blood flow, partial oxygen pressure, mitochondrial NADH redox state, and extracellular potassium. The model is also demonstrates pathological conditions, such as complete and partial ischemia, cortical spreading depression under normoxic and partial ischemic conditions by processing collected parameters' data. This application provides computing other parameters from equations by mensuration of one or two related parameters to help experts recognize patients' conditions during clinical operations. All mathematical variables of model are only time dependent ('point-model' approach) and Simulink application based on this approach.

Keywords— Spreading Depression; Modeling of Brain; Brain Metabolism; Modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

Brain ischemia is a condition in which there is insufficient blood flow to the brain to meet metabolic demand [1]. This leads to poor oxygen supply or cerebral hypoxia and thus to the death of brain tissue or cerebral infarction / ischemic stroke [2]. It is a sub-type of stroke along with subarachnoid hemorrhage and intracerebral hemorrhage [3]. Ischemia leads to alterations in brain metabolism, reduction in metabolic rates, and energy crisis [4]. There are different types of ischemia such as complete and partial ischemia, cortical spreading depression under normoxic and partial ischemic conditions.

Severe ischemia results in metabolic stress, resulting in the depletion of essential energy metabolites, including ATP and phosphocreatine [5], [6]. Anoxic injury can lead to potassium-induced release of excitatory amino acids, the opening of glutamate receptor associated ion channels and the influx of Ca²⁺ [7], [8], [9]. With reperfusion, these metabolite levels may normalize, indicating normalization of cellular functions and ion homeostasis. In models of TBI like those of cerebral ischemia, the degree of metabolic stress is dependent upon injury severity [10], [11]. Mild or moderate injury is usually not associated with severe metabolic changes such as prolonged decreases in ATP and increase in lactate levels [12]. However, after more severe TBI, disturbances in ion homeostasis including cellular efflux of potassium, influx of calcium and sodium ions occur [13]. A complex pattern of glucose metabolism has been reported after TBI in animal models [14] as well as in patient studies [15]. In several investigations, acute increases in glucose metabolism followed by prolonged reductions in glucose utilization have been documented [16], [17]. The degree of metabolic stress as well as tissue oxygen delivery appear to be critical factors in determining whether or not cerebral ischemia plays an important role in cell injury mechanisms following TBI.

Mathematical models concerns oxidative metabolism in the cerebral cortex, describing oxygen transport from the capillaries to the tissue during functional activation [18]. In this approach, the partial pressure of oxygen in cerebral tissue was calculated from the diffusion equation for general cone-shaped tissue geometry. By this model, the behavior of the oxidative metabolic rate during functional activation was predicted.

In a series of reports, mathematical models were applied to study the processes underlying the pathogenesis of tissue damage [19], [20], [21]. Aiming at the investigation of the lengthwise propagation of the tissue damage and taking into account the spatial heterogeneity of the tissue, the authors of the above-referenced works had to consider both the temporal and spatial variability of several key metabolic variables characterizing the tissue state. In contrast, we confine ourselves to a so-called ‘point model,’ where all the variables representing physiological parameters depend on time only [22].

According to previous researches, in the framework of our research, we refer to the tissue as a whole, i.e., as a self-contained system with inputs and outputs. This simplification enables us to utilize the so-called integral- or point-model approach, when the physiological variables are regarded as functions of time only (their interdependence apart), rather than as space-distributed variables. Hence, the “diffusion” terms and the spatial derivatives that appear in the space-distributed models [20], [21] are omitted, and we arrive at a classical dynamic system, whose states are described by ordinary differential equations of the kinetic type. Furthermore, using this approach, we can tune the model, maximizing the fit to the actual clinical and experimental data with little risk of over fitting. In the course of data fitting, different kinds of nonlinearities in the right-hand parts of the differential equations were tested. The main objective was to keep the model physiologically meaningful, simple as possible, and universal in the sense that the same values of the model parameters would be used to simulate the normal and different pathological conditions of the brain tissue. The goodness-of-fit was examined and confirmed in numerous independent runs using various laboratories and clinical data published earlier [23], [24], [25], [26], [27]. The mathematical model manifests many of the essential characteristics of the experimental data with regard to certain observable variables, providing a quantitative fit, which is indicative of the model’s reliability. We have tested the ability of the model to correctly reproduce the dynamics of a reduced number of the physiological variables when the dynamics of the remaining variables are inputted in the model. This property of our model may be used in clinical practice to complement real-time measurements.

II. MATHEMATIAL MODELING

Our model is based on the assumption that the tissue functional state is fully determined by the following metabolic variables:

Concentration of extracellular potassium (K), Rate of potassium reuptake (R), Blood flow (F), Oxygen (O), NADH (N), Partial impairment (P)

Such a formulation of the model was selected because quantitative data on the rates of change of the model variables

are scarce. In clinical conditions, only some of the above tissue parameters, such as the blood flow, the concentration of extracellular potassium, and the level of NADH, can be measured. Other, hidden variables (the rate of potassium reuptake, partial impairment, and the level of oxygen) are either non-measurable or not measured at the present. Their meaning of the model variables is detailed below.

The model is constructed as a set of nonlinear differential equations (see below (1)–(6)) that govern the temporal evolution of the above metabolic variables. Each of the main tissue variables, being a function of time, depends also on other physiological variables. Its dynamics are governed by an equation that describes the variable’s behavior under both normoxic and pathological conditions. All variables of the model (including time) are non-dimensional, i.e., they are normalized through some scales. To enable computations, these variables are discretized. Thus, each of the above six variables ranges from 0 to 1 while time runs from 0 to 500 units (with some small step).

In the equations, the variables are denoted by a single capital letter (e.g., K , R), while their specific levels—by the same letter with a subscript (e.g., K_{rest}); multiplicative constant factors are denoted by a capital “ C ” and subscripted by a number of indices—capital letters usually designating the related variables. The first index identifies the variable whose dynamic equation contains this constant, while the remaining indices (those appearing after the comma) identify the variables that the constant C modulates. The subscripts ‘rest’ and ‘max,’ respectively, designate the resting value and the absolute ceiling of a variable. The resting value $F_{rest} = F_{max} / 2$ is equal to the normal level of the blood flow. The initial values of the variables in the model reflect normoxic tissue state.

The equations governing the temporal behavior of the metabolic parameters indicated above are constructed on the following grounds.

The rate of change of the extracellular potassium concentration, K , is modeled as a reaction-diffusion process, which is governed by four terms:

$$\frac{dK}{dt} = C_{K,K}(K - K_{rest})(K - K_U)(K - K_{Max}) + (\delta + P)(K_{Max} - K) - C_{K,R}KR + K_{inj} \quad (1)$$

The first, ‘reaction’ term in Eq. (1) models the regenerative processes that generate the sharp rise of extracellular potassium concentration occurring when K crosses the thresholds level K . The second term represents the diffusion of intracellular potassium in undamaged tissue and intracellular potassium release to the extracellular space resulting from various tissue stresses; here constant represents the rate of permanent intracellular potassium leakage in normal tissue; for the meaning of P see Eq. (6) and the

explanation appearing immediately before it. The third term reflects the reuptake of potassium by Na/K ATPase pumps. The last term represents an external injection of potassium.

The rate of potassium reuptake, R , is modeled by the following equation:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = C_{R,NOKR}(K - K_{rest})(R_{Max} - R) - C_{R,RK}R(K_{Max} - K) \quad (2)$$

Two terms in Eq. (2) affect the rate of potassium reuptake, reflecting the functioning of Na/K pumps. The first term in the right-hand part of (2) models the increase of reuptake with increasing levels of NADH and oxygen. The second term gradually brings Na/K ATPase activity back to its resting level when K values are restored.

The blood flow F is regulated by the equation

$$\frac{dF}{dt} = C_{F,FO}(F_{Max} - F)(O_{rest} - O) + C_{F,F}\left(\frac{F_{Max}}{2} - F\right) - C_{F,KF}(K - K_{rest})(F_{rest} - F) \quad (3)$$

Here the first term represents the dependence of blood supply on the oxygen status and the current flow level. The second term in (3) self-regulates the blood flow toward its base rate. The third term describes variations in the blood flow caused by an irregular extracellular potassium rise (that may result, e.g., from an injection of potassium). When constructing the last term, the previous tissue state has been taken into account. For that purpose, the coefficient $C_{FK} = 0$, if the previous value of the blood flow is less than the resting value F_{rest} , otherwise it is taken to equal 0.5.

The energy status of the tissue is determined by oxygen, O . Its level is determined by a competition between the supply and demand terms. The supply term is proportional to the blood flow and current oxygen level. The demand term is an equivalent consumption rate; it involves the oxygen, potassium reuptake rate, and NADH. The resulting equation is:

$$\frac{dO}{dt} = C_{O,FO}F(O_{Max} - O) - C_{O,NRO}N(RO)^{0.5} \quad (4)$$

The rate of NADH change is determined by its level, while the consumption rate depends on the potassium reuptake as well as on oxygen:

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = C_{N,N}(N_{Max} - N) - C_{N,NRO}N(RO)^{0.5} \quad (5)$$

Finally, the level of stresses experienced by the tissue is represented by the partial impairment variable P . Its meaning can be understood from Eq. (1): stresses upset the integrity of tissue cells, which results in increasing diffusion of the intracellular potassium to the extracellular space. In a damaging situation, the stores of oxygen deplete, and O becomes insufficient for the Na/K pump functioning. The

concentration of extracellular potassium rises and the partial impairment augments. The corresponding equation is:

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = C_{P,OK}(O_{MIN} - O)(K - K_{rest}) \quad (6)$$

The simulation of the different pathophysiological tissue conditions was carried out in the following way:

A variety of ischemic events can be produced if, in Eq. (3), we set $F_{max} < 1$ within a time interval $t_1 < t < t_2$. To mimic the initiation of spreading depression, potassium infusion is simulated, i.e., $K_{inj} > 0$, during a designated time interval.

Ischemia will happen when Eq.3 in period of $t_1 < t < t_2$, F_{max} goes to $F_{max} < 1$.

TABLE I. The model coefficients and constants used in simulations.

Parameters	Constant value
F_{rest}	0.5
K_{rest}	0.3
K_{inj}	0.18 during injection, otherwise 0
N_{rest}	0.4
O_{rest}	0.48
R_{rest}	0.3
P_{rest}	0
K	0.2
$C_{K,K}$	-0.24
$C_{K,R}$	0.08
$C_{E,KF}$	0 if $F < F_{rest}$, otherwise 0.5
$C_{F,FO}$	0.75
$C_{F,F}$	0.6
$C_{R,NOKR}$	1.4
$C_{R,K}$	0.048
$C_{O,FO}$	0.1
$C_{O,NRO}$	0.18
$C_{N,N}$	0.5
$C_{N,NRO}$	2
$C_{P,OK}$	0.15
	0.01

III. SIMULINK MODEL

In this section, we present Simulink model for mathematical model of brain metabolism energy discussed above. First and foremost, we determined coefficients and constants.

Fig. 1, Simulink model for equation 1

In this section we consider subsystem for each section.

Fig. 2, Simulink model related to equation 2

Equation no.2 refers to potassium density changes.

Fig. 3, Simulink model related to equation 3

Fig.3 related to reabsorption of potassium

Fig. 4, Simulink model for equation 4

Equation no.4 related to blood flow changes. And fig.4 refers to Simulink model of Eq.4

Fig. 5, Simulink model refers to Eq.5

Equation no.5 refers to slight changes of oxygen pressure. And fig.5 refers to Simulink model of Eq.5

Fig. 6, Simulink model related to equation 6

Fig.6 refers to Simulink model of Eq.6 which related to variation of NADH

Fig. 7, Simulink model for variation tissue damage changes

IV. SIMULATING AN EVALUATION OF SIMULINK BIOLOGICAL MODEL

For evaluation Eq.4 we define coefficients and constants from TABLE.I.

The pathological state of spreading depression can be induced by washing the cerebral cortex with a diluted solution of KCl (the “potassium injection”). This is modeled by putting $K_{inj} > 0$ within the time interval $t1 < t < t2$. When spreading depression is induced, the increase in energy requirement leads to the activation of $Na^+ - K^+$ ATPase in order to restore the normal potassium distribution, and causes an increase in blood flow and a decrease in NADH.

This model simulated by external potassium injection during 60 second.

$$K_{inj} = 0.18 [-0.75e^{-t/350} - 0.25e^{-t/300} u(t-60) + [0.02e^{-t/30} + 0.01e^{-t/2} + 1] u(t-120), F_{max} = 1$$

Fig.8. F_{max} input since spreading depression

Fig.9. resulted diagram from simulation by Matlab Simulink since spreading depression

In this case, the blood flow decreases mildly ($F_{max} = 0.5$ within the time interval from $t1$ to $t2$), but within the ischemic period, an infusion of potassium is modeled. K_{inj} is assumed to be positive within a relatively short time interval contained in the interval $t1 < t < t2$ during which the main events occur. Accordingly, the blood flow slightly decreases as a result of the infusion, and then increases to the new resting level.

$$K_{inj} = 0.18 [-0.75e^{-t/350} - 0.25e^{-t/300} u(t-120) + [0.02e^{-t/30} + 0.01e^{-t/2} + 1] u(t-180)$$

Fig.10. resulted diagram from simulation by Matlab Simulink since spreading depression during partial ischemia

Global Ischemia occurs if the blood flow drops to zero. To simulate this condition, F_{max} is set equal to zero in Eq. (3), within the time interval from $t1$ to $t2$ (Fig.7), which signifies that the energy supply terminated, and the Na^+ / K^+ pump ceased to operate. This causes an increase in NADH and extracellular potassium to their maxima. In the recovery process, when $t > t2$, the blood flow increases and reaches a level higher than its resting level (the overshoot or hyperemic response).

$$F_{max} = u(t) - u(t-40) + e^{-t/4} u(t-39.9) + [-0.5e^{-t/0.3} - 0.5e^{-t/7} + 1] u(t-190), C_{F, KF} = u(t) - u(t-42.77) + u(t-192), K_{inj} = 0$$

Result shown by Fig.11

Fig.11. F_{max} input in complete ischemia

Fig.12. resulted diagram from simulation by Matlab Simulink in complete ischemia

In partial ischemia with depolarization, blood flow will slightly decrease and a smaller percentage of ischemia time will equal to zero. Inputs will consider as:

$$F_{\max} = u(t) - u(t-39.9) + [0.75e^{-t/5} + 0.25e^{-t/25}]u(t-40) + [-0.5e^{-t/5} - 0.5e^{-t/15} + 1]u(t-190), C_F, K_F = u(t) - u(t-43.85) + u(t-208), K_{inj} = 0$$

Result shown by Fig. 13

Fig.13. F_{\max} input in partial ischemia with depolarization

Fig.14. resulted diagram from simulation by Matlab Simulink in partial ischemia with depolarization

In partial ischemia without depolarization condition, blood flow did not equal to zero. However, it will decrease till 0.5 and it will back to normal condition after 2.50 minutes. Therefore, diagram changes slightly and smooth. Inputs will consider as:

$$F_{\max} = u(t) - u(t-40) + [0.357e^{-t/5} + 0.125e^{-t/10}]u(t-42) + 0.5[-0.5e^{-t/5} - 0.5e^{-t/15} + 1]u(t-190), C_F, K_F = 0.5, K_{inj} = 0$$

Result shown by Fig. 15

Fig.15. F_{\max} input in partial ischemia without depolarization

Fig.12. resulted diagram from simulation by Matlab Simulink in partial ischemia without depolarization

V. CONCLUSION

Through simulating this model in normal condition, the value of variables will obtain. By this model we can calculate other parameters from equations by mensuration of one or two related parameters to help experts realizing patient conditions during clinical operations. Our results demonstrate the potential of the computational mathematical model of tissue metabolism to describe the pathogenesis of tissue sustains in various clinical and experimental situations. The model simulates five pathophysiological tissue conditions. NADH redox states during ischemia [26]. On the other hand, high levels of extracellular potassium produced in spreading

depression (SD) lead to an increase in the tissue metabolic demands, as indicated by a rise in O₂ consumption. This process is usually accompanied by an increase in blood flow; as a result, the activation of mitochondrial activity leads to NADH oxidation. It is expected that by using this device in various clinical situations, the three parameters provided will permit diagnosing the tissue metabolic state,

Even though, extracellular K⁺ and O₂ level are not monitored. Joining these measurements with the data processing by our model will open up the possibility of

Expanding the scope of experiments where the control parameters F_{max} , K_{inj} , and the time of injection would alter within given realistic intervals. The aim of such experiments will be the evaluation of the optimal values (or frames) of the variables that determine the required behaviors of NADH and oxygen.

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